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L. Otroshchenko, T. Povalii, 2020

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**Olga Boyko¹, Anna Jeremus-Lewandowska²,
Larysa Otroshchenko¹, Tatiana Povalii¹**

¹ Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine

² Ignacy Jan Paderewski Academy of Music in Poznan, Poznan, Poland

Trainings Usage in the Professional Education of Future Socio-Cultural Activity Managers

Abstract: *Introduction.* The relevance of the socio-cultural field is growing now. There is a necessity of highlighting the innovative forms of future socio-cultural activity managers' education, connected with manager activity content, dealing with keeping and sharing of cultural values management. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is theoretical analysis, systematization, and generalization of the scientific research concerning the justification of trainings usage peculiarities in future socio-cultural activity managers' education. In the course of the research, such general scientific methods as analysis, synthesis, systematization, and generalization of theoretical issues have been used, as well as specific scientific methods of terminological, retrospective, systematic-structural, and structural-functional analysis. *Results.* Key moments in the history of trainings emergence and development have been highlighted. Kinds of trainings have been analysed: personal-oriented, skills-building, marketing, managerial, staff training, and organizational ones. The structure of trainings preparation in the professional education of future socio-cultural managers has been systematized, which is specified under the following indicators: stages, sections, aim, examples of implementation. Trainings content has been analysed and its illustrative subject matter has been presented. Teacher-trainer personal qualities have been distinguished, and his professional excellence elements have been detected. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of obtained results is in the concretization of the concept "training", systematization of training preparation structure, and providing illustrative subject matter of trainings

for future socio-cultural activity managers' education; practical value is in the possibility of obtained results usage in the universities' education process.

Keywords: manager, socio-cultural activity, training, teacher-trainer, professional excellence.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The process of European and World integration causes fundamental changes in the field of social-economic relations: the fast pace of different scientific and technical spheres development contributes to the transformation of civic consciousness. As a result, we can observe changes in the processes and directions of thinking, in the worldview of contemporary people and the formation of a renewed sphere of behavior culture, and society members' relationships. Consequently, we can observe the transformation of education. Modern educational processes cannot and should not be outside changes' frames. They should correspond to these changes and social development and meet personality needs in the process of professional knowledge acquisition.

In recent years, realization and theoretical conceptualization of socio-cultural activity in this country takes place in a context of changes and transformations, caused by the globalization processes. Obviously, there is dependence strengthening between states and nations as well as we can see international cooperation expansion, in particular in cultural and educational spheres, and systematic formation of unified world cultural and educational areas. Consequently, this causes an increase in global society's cultural diversity. Considering all the above, and in terms of fast world changes, socio-cultural manager activity becomes more relevant, as it substantially influences cultural society development trends, especially in towns and villages, contributing to the creation of unified cultural areas according to the needs of the developed state.

Undoubtedly, state standards change demands on the educational process and its results. This phenomenon involves the implementation of new technologies and their practical engagement in the educational process of universities. Thereby, one of the most qualitative models of future socio-cultural management professional education is its training format, which allows not only effective technologies (methods, forms, techniques) acquisition, managerial decision-making, and business communication, but also students' individual peculiarities discovery. Besides, in the process of the training, students actively exchange experience, thus, improving their skills and knowledge in the field of scientific-research and production-practical activity. As a result, in the context of our investigation, we consider training as the primary organizational form of future socio-cultural managers' education as it allows these specialists to unlock their

creative abilities, to take part in discussions, to get consultations, to analyze and solve problems.

State study of the problem. The problem of trainings' usage in the professional education of future specialists has always been in the center of attention, in particular, its such aspects as methodological peculiarities of professional training (S. Makshanov (1992), I. Vachkov (1999), V. Pozhydaev (2008), I. Korniienko and S. Almashi (2016), A. Vorontcov and E. Vorontcova (2010) and others), different trainings' design and conducting (T. Fulei, N. Burukovska, T. Budnychenko and H. Savchenko (2017), I. Kurtikova, K. Lavrova and V. Li (2005), O. Shevchuk (2011) and others), trainings' benefit for the future specialists' development (N. Liapkusov (2013), N. Yakovchenko (2007), M. Churkin and N. Zhadko (2006), S. Gladyshev (2005) and others).

Much attention is paid last time to the problem of different kinds of trainings' study (educational, psychological, IT, communicative). Ukrainian researcher L. Bondarieva (2006) proves that educational training should be considered as a pedagogical technology of education as it has a precise algorithm of its implementation and guarantees planned result achievement (p. 14).

To S. Kuryliuk's mind, the advantage of psychological training is in its unique ability to study complex, significant issues of personal development in a safe training environment, unlike real life with its threats and risks. The scientist believes that the positive results of psychotraining impact contribute to the constructive system of relations' formation with friends, colleagues, and relatives (Kuryliuk, 2008, p. 17).

Specialists in the educational sphere are unanimous in their opinion that IT and communicative trainings play an important role in the educational process. Thus, Ukrainian researcher O. Grek (2009) states that IT training leads to the development of future specialists' visual originality, their strategic-semantic flexibility, and operational components of visual thinking (p. 13). In her turn, N. Lukianchuk (2014) sees the main advantage of communicative training in the active interaction of all the participants in the process of which they learn to act in unexpected situations in a new way and to implement obtained listening techniques and statements (p. 76).

Unresolved issues. Although interest in the training form of education continues to grow, there is a lack of materials concerning methodological, theoretical, and technological issues of training' usage in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers. The questions of educational training model design, organizational-pedagogical stages of training programs creation, demands to the personality of a teacher-trainer, and his methodical competence have not been appropriately studied.

Thus, the relevance of this research is confirmed by the importance of quality future socio-cultural activity managers' professional education, the requirement of their practical managerial skills and abilities formation, the necessity of creation of conditions for students' creative potential, and lack of this issue scientific-methodical base.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the article. One of the demands of the realization of the socio-cultural activity manager's educational bachelor program is the implementation in the educational process of interactive forms of lessons' conduction with the purpose of students' professional practical formation and development. The advantage of this kind of teaching is students' motivation to the intensive actions, stimulation to the mutual exchange of thoughts and ideas, providing feedback, etc. That is why, practical lessons, containing exercises, trainings, exact situations analysis, modeling, forecasting of socio-cultural processes play an essential role in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers.

Thus, the purpose of this article is the theoretical analysis, systematization, and synthesis of scientific research concerning validation of trainings' usage peculiarities in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers.

The methodological basis of the study. The methodological basis of the research is a historical approach, which gives an opportunity to consider the emergence and development of the practical activity sphere. Within the historical approach, we used the comparative-historical method, which allowed us to research the similarity and difference of the concept "training" in different cultures and on various stages of the educational process.

With the help of the terminological approach, we made the description, analysis, and clarification of terminological vocabulary, namely the notion "training". The systematic approach is used to consider a socio-cultural activity manager as integrity, which has certain connections and components of professional competence.

A structural-functional approach helps to set aside structural components in the system (training) and to define their functions. This approach enables us to identify various connections of entity components and to distinguish substantial and unsubstantial, relevant, and random ones among them.

Systematic and activity approach, being very important in scientific research, and namely in pedagogics lately, allows researching such educational component as training in a complex way in accordance with possibilities of

future socio-cultural activity managers in the combination of theory and practice. This approach allows considering training as a form of future managers' interactive education, in the process of which various kinds of socio-cultural activity are used. With the help of the axiological approach, based on the values, allowing us to study socio-cultural events from the point of view of set opportunities of personality satisfaction; we have carried out the analysis of the training's quality as the pedagogical form of work and future specialists' satisfaction.

Research methods. In the course of the research, we have used mutually supporting methods of analysis and synthesis, with the help of which we have considered the concept "training", its kinds, forms and subject matter. Methods of generalization and systematization, which are closely connected with analysis and synthesis, allowed us to specify the concept "training" as a model of active learning. With the help of the retrospective method, we have analyzed vital moments in the history of trainings' emergence and development. Method of terminological analysis allowed us to organize the notion-terminological research apparatus. Systematic-structural and structural-functional methods were used with the purpose of determination of the training's preparation structure in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers.

Research information base. Obtained results are based on the theoretical and methodological works of Ukrainian scientists in the field of pedagogics, management, and socio-cultural activity. In the course of the research, we have used methodical literature of the departments of Sumy State University, and namely: Department of Foreign Languages, Department of Psychology, Political Science and Socio-Cultural Technologies.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The history of trainings' emergence and development

Market socio-economic relations in the country, having changed production relations character, have made new, higher demands to the labor, working relationships, specialties' nomenclature content, and above all, to the specialists' qualification, professional proficiency, knowledge, abilities, and skills. New types of professionals such as an entrepreneur, a businessperson, etc. have appeared in the nomenclature of new enterprises, firms, organizations, and in governing bodies, working both in state and in private sectors. As for the socio-cultural sphere, the following specialists work here as managers, art-managers, tourism managers, exhibition managers, producers, showmen, promoters, impresarios, etc. To our mind, these specialists should professionally

possess management and marketing technologies in commercial and uncommercial activity, be enterprising, energetic, and competent in economics and jurisprudence, possess professional self-awareness, organizational skills, and be able to achieve results and success.

We must confess that increased demands to manager's professionalism and his administrative direction have not met adequate realization in university's teaching and educational process system and in its main subsystems: technological, professional-personal, and social-psychological ones. At the same time, new specialties were affirmed by state education standards of higher education, demanding their scientific conceptualization, new conceptual approaches, theoretic-methodological support of educational process, and professional self-determination. Among them, one should mention such specialty as "Management of Socio-Cultural Activity" (qualification "Manager of Socio-Cultural Activity").

Universities have guided their efforts towards searching for adequate and dynamic measures concerning the realization of the holistic process of specialists' education, the formation of the professional-managerial orientation of a manager, and his adaptation to the real labor activity. Thus, one of the crucial instruments in the system of future socio-cultural activity managers' education is a training, which main peculiarity has become intensive knowledge transition and formation of professional-managerial skills and abilities within a brief time period (one or three days) directly in the process of the educational process.

We would like to address the history of training's appearance and development. As a unique form of education, trainings appeared in Western countries relatively recently – in the 40th of the XX century. *Kurt Lewin*, a German and American psychologist, is considered to be the founder of the training in its modern form. Kurt Lewin created the Centre on studying group dynamics in the USA after II World War. It is assumed that trainings held by K. Lewin's students in Bethel (USA), were directed on communicative competence development. Those trainings got the name T-group (Yakovchenko, 2007).

During his research, Kurt Lewin concluded that the majority of effective personal changes take place in the group, but not in a specific context. As a result of the intergroup relations workshop's successful work, the National training laboratory was created in 1947 in the USA (Pozhydaev, 2008, p. 7).

We should mention that we can find examples of modern trainings in the description of military, religious, and fine arts educational process. Thus, at the beginning of the XX century, *K. Stanislavski* and his followers proposed numerous exercises for the training of actors. In the 60th last century, a social and life skills training campaign was created, which was used for the professional education of managers with the purpose of their psychological

support and development, relied upon the humanistic psychology of *K. Rogers* (Yakovchenko, 2007). The social-psychological method was designed in the 70th under the supervision of *M. Forverg* in Leipzig und Jena Universities. Role-plays with elements of dramatization were tools in the training as they create conditions for effective communicative skills (Pozhydaev, 2008, p. 7).

3.2. The concept “training”, its purpose and tasks

We must confess that scientists interpret the concept of “training” differently now. This concept is specified mainly in specialized terminological dictionaries. Thus, in the pedagogical dictionary of *G. Kodzhaspirova* and *A. Kodzhaspirov* (2005), “training” is defined as a form of interactive learning, the purpose of which is competence development in the field of interpersonal and professional behavior in communication (p. 268). In Oxford English Thesaurus of *J. Simpson* and *E. Weiner* (1989) “training” is interpreted as “the process of obtaining skills, which are necessary for work performance; the process of getting ready to the participation in the sports competitions with the help of physical exercises”. In the *Sociological Encyclopedic Dictionary*, the concept “training” as characterized as practice, during which one obtains skills and abilities in any sphere (Osipov, 1998, p. 375).

We should emphasize, that there is no single scientific approach as for the definition of the concept “training” now; scientists distinguish some paradigms in its definition, and namely:

1) Scientist *N. Liapkusov* (2013) considers “training” as “the model of active teaching, which is realized in intensive form, aiming to the development of necessary personal and business qualities, motivation attitudes, values, specific knowledge, skills, and abilities, which allow raising personal efficiency or organization competitiveness in the short term” (pp. 71-72);

2) According to the definition of a Doctor of Psychological Sciences *S. Makshanov* (1992), “training” is “the way to reprogram the model of personal behavior and activity management; the process of new behavioral functions creation (or development of existing ones)” (p. 81);

3) In his turn, scientist *S. Gladyshev* (2005) defines the concept “training” as a specific method of knowledge acquisition, specially created by the favorable environment, where everyone can see and realize his pluses and minuses, understand what personal qualities and professional skills are necessary for carrying out one’s professional activity (p. 70).

Thus, in the context of research, we consider “training” as a form of interactive future managers’ teaching, in the process of which the collection of

various kinds of socio-cultural activity is used, providing objective character of this process, as cultural-artistic programs design abilities, as well as abilities to present information, to use professional tools, to express thoughts clearly, to provoke the partner to do the same is the main component of the future socio-cultural activity manager job description.

Now we would like to define the training's aim and to formulate its specific tasks. The training's aim is to create conditions for the student's professional development and self-perfection, in terms of which we can form and master their subject knowledge, as well as declarative and procedural knowledge concerning cultural-leisure programs and cultural-mass events conducting for the different population categories. On the base of this knowledge, we can develop corresponding skills and abilities as components of future socio-cultural activity managers' professional education. The aim is realized in the course of specific training tasks: 1) experience sharing through direct und demonstration of actions, methods, ways and forms logics of socio-cultural commenting activity; 2) obtained professional knowledge consumption in practical situations; 3) professional knowledge acquisition and adjustment; 4) cognitive motivation increase; 5) fostering more qualitative understanding of the future professional activity purpose and context; 6) business communication and public speaking skills development; 7) participants' personal, professional skills reflexing as for the design and realization of various cultural-leisure programs; 8) fostering the formation of a future manager of socio-cultural activity, personal and professional position.

3.3. Classification of trainings

We would like to consider the classification of trainings' types. It is not perfect due to the variety of interpretations of this concept as a didactic category. In our opinion, the best review of the trainings' types was introduced by the *Russian training-center "Sinton"* (2014), which were united under certain features (*Figure 1*).

Let us consider these trainings in detail:

1) during personal-oriented training, students get acquainted with the vast world of psychology and philosophy, get to know the basics of ethics and behavior culture in the trainings. As a rule, this kind of training is "relatively easy" and practically does not touch the personal participant's identity. The warm and friendly atmosphere during training provokes open sincere conversation and group discussion of the training's subject matter (Sinton, 2014);

2) the purpose of skill-building training is awareness level raising concerning leadership issues, students' professional communicating forming, allowing interacting with other people while doing training tasks, self-esteem increase,

self-assurance developing. This kind of training can be grouped into the following types: interaction with society, staff, unknown people; interaction with the opposite sex; business interaction with other people with the purpose of business and career development (Sinton, 2014);

Figure 1. Types of trainings
Source: own development

3) in the process of marketing training students obtain tactics and marketing management strategy in the enterprise; they namely obtain skills of creative search of directions and reserves of upgrading of processes and management methods of enterprise marketing activity, solve exact marketing tasks and execute corresponding functions of marketing organizational structures (Bilovodska, 2010);

4) managerial training allows future socio-cultural activity managers to get information on management skills and methods of their most active implementation, to learn and to use the most effective ways of staff management properly, to be able to choose the optimal variant of solving social, cultural and economic problems considering real circumstances (Sinton, 2014);

5) organizational training is considered as a means of intensive acquisition of self-development and productive collective work organization experience by future socio-cultural activity managers. We would like to mention main principles, which are laid down in its basis: intensive feedback, mutual trust, openness to new things, the actualization of reserve opportunities of the group and their members. This type of training is one of the methods of teaching students organizational skills and abilities, as well as the ability to develop oneself as an organizer (Shcherbina, 2004);

6) the purpose of staff training is a formation of students' vision as for effective search technology of new employees, team formation, introduction to the position, interpersonal interaction, conflicts resolution, etc. (Sinton, 2014).

We would like to emphasize that in the process of future socio-cultural activity managers education all the kinds of trainings mentioned above should be used as allow to cover various subject blocks of professional information, thus developing professional competence, verifying learning material, engaging every student to fulfill specific tasks in exact activity type, creating and presenting own projects, corresponding main directions of modern socio-cultural manager activity, using additional sources.

3.4. The structure and the content of the training

Let us consider the structure of the training's preparation and content. Thus, scientists present some algorithms of training's development, and namely:

1) algorithm by *T. Fulei* (Fulei et al., 2017) – defining planned results and kind of development, selection of content material, structuring of educational material according to interactive learning methods, designing of training's agenda;

2) general algorithm – defining planned results and kind of development, creation of the technological concept, defining client's technologies, defining trainer's technologies (Korniienko & Almashi, 2016, p. 44);

3) algorithm by *Yevgeny Machnyev* – learning group, aims formulating, brainstorming of activities types, working with the list, designing the sequence of activity types and their selection, different forms of group work, different styles and channels of cognition (Vorontcov & Vorontcova, 2010, pp. 28-29).

In our investigation, we concentrated on the training's development, which is built mainly according to the algorithm by *T. Fulei*. We made it more concrete under the following indicators: work stages, sections of steps, aim, and content of steps, examples of application (*Table 1*).

Thus, during training's planning and development, a teacher tries to organize it in such a way that to be able not only to transfer knowledge but also to develop their skills and abilities to fulfill production and managerial tasks; creation of cultural-leisure programs; useful professional tools application; organization of public civic events; holding of the presentation of the sociocultural projects. The teacher's responsibilities and his actions are directed to the creation of such circumstances, in which students will be able to develop their professional competence.

Further, we would like to analyze training content that is the in-group discussion of various professional problems. The main content of such teaching form is experience transfer and exchange. Training's benefit compared to other forms of future socio-cultural activity managers' vocational education is in the fact that students are active participants of new experience acquisition. This

experience is introduced in a visible and figurative way, and involves deep combination of theory and practice. The main idea is original and high informative environment creation, stimulating creative and reflexive future specialists' activity (particularly, socio-cultural activity managers).

Table 1. Structure of training's development in the vocational education of future socio-cultural activity managers

Stages	Sections of the stage	Aims and content of the stage
1	2	3
Stage of aims and expected results definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - definition of main future socio-cultural activity managers professional competence components - formulating of educational purposes and expected results 	<p><i>Aim:</i> the setting of the subject, aims, and tasks; outlining the problematic matters and expected results; organizing group work</p> <p><i>Content:</i> tasks definition (socio-cultural, technological, organizational, marketing, culturological, humanitarian, psychological and political), abilities (general and special) and skills (general scientific and professional) of the future socio-cultural activity managers; formulating of educational purposes (studying, developing process promotion, creative potential realization, optimal level achievement, research); formulating expected results (required tasks performance, creation, organization, carrying out, etc.)</p>
<p><i>Examples of implementation:</i> to study the fields of cultural and creative industries, to promote the process of future socio-cultural activity managers abilities development, to achieve the optimal level of managerial decisions, to research current socio-cultural situation, to raise the level of communicative skills, to identify event-management technologies, to solve manufacturing or managerial tasks, to create the cultural-leisure program, to use toolbox effectively, to organize the public civic event, to make the presentation of socio-cultural project</p>		
Stage of content material selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - structured plan design - identification of educational material content and volume 	<p><i>Aim:</i> identification of material content and volume, which are necessary to use for the set goals achievement</p> <p><i>Content:</i> plan design with the list of topics in the form of points with the division into subtopics; identification of educational material content and volume, considering its types</p>
<p><i>Examples of implementation:</i> materials, designed directly by a trainer (mini-lectures, presentations, tasks for small groups, individual work and processing, brainstorming questions, questions for express-questionnaires, analytical schemes for completing, tests); reference materials (regulatory and legal acts, materials of socio-cultural experience, video materials, scripts, etc.)</p>		

Extension of Table 1

1	2	3
Stage of educational material structuring	- educational material structuring according to the interactive teaching methods	<i>Aim:</i> educational material structuring realization, considering teaching methods <i>Content:</i> orientation in the full range of teaching methods, choosing the best teaching methods for specific results achievement, the combination of teaching and learning methods for educational goals achievement, ability to change, and to replace teaching methods in the case of necessity
<i>Examples of implementation:</i> play methods – dramatization, imitation; structural exercises – acquaintance, expectation, conclusions; movement exercises – work in small groups; express-questionnaire – questions and answering them, using software Turning Point; demonstration – presentation of teacher’s tasks, video clips; situational methods – widescreen situation, micro situation, situation-illustration, situational task, situation-incident; “Brainstorming” – participants’ ideas generation, ideas assessment and selection of the best ones; analysis of the specific situational task – script design, its analysis, problem-solving; work in small groups; plenary discussion; interview; modeling, etc.		
Stage of agenda design	- agenda formation for a teacher - agenda formation for participants	<i>Aim:</i> agenda formation based on the defined educational goals and expected training results according to roles and functions distribution of both participants and teachers <i>Content:</i> formation of extended and detailed agenda; thinking over the sequence of educational activity types (topics and educational methods change), using the practical model “movement in a circle”
<i>Examples of implementation:</i> expanded and detailed agenda includes educational goals and expected training’s result, time limits, educational goals and expected results, teaching methods and practical tasks types, aim of each practical lesson, list of handouts; the practical model “movement in a circle” usage, including four sequential phases – personal experience actualization, analysis and reflection, new knowledge comprehension and its generalization, experimental testing of new knowledge and its implementation in practice		

Source: developed on the basis of (Fulei et al., 2017)

O. Shevchuk (2011) considers the training lesson from the point of view of its two components content and process. In her opinion, the professional subject area (ideas, questions, phenomena, etc.) refers to the content. Students master it in the process of education, as for the training process, it is connected with the interaction of its participants, and namely with the atmosphere in the collective, roles distribution, influence on each other (p. 43).

We concluded that scientists consider training in two directions. The first one is the more methods used in training, the better; the second direction – the more topics covered in one training, the more effective the education is. Thus, we should point out that information volume does not guarantee its practical usage (Churkina & Zhadko, 2006, p. 92).

Further, we would like to analyze oriented trainings subject area in the contest of future socio-cultural activity managers' education, which we systematized according to the trainings types (personal-oriented, skill-building, marketing, managerial, organizational, staff ones). This subject area can be:

1) personal-oriented training – resources activity and efficiency management; moral activity (the problem of the action moral assessment); behavioral strategies in the ethnic conflict; spirituality and esthetic self-revealing of creative personality; personal-professional characteristics of a leader (Kupenko, 2019, p. 7; Boiko, 2019a, p. 6; Lebid, 2019, p. 7; Svitailo & Dementov, 2019, p. 14);

2) skill-building training – team building and teamwork; psychological training and coaching in the teambuilding practice; staff selection for the strategy design; mapping as an instrument of influence and development of the modern Ukrainian cultural programs; organization of the individual work in the university (Svitaylo & Dementov, 2019, p. 16; Onishchenko, 2019, p. 7; Pobozhii, 2019, p. 7; Boiko, 2019b, p. 7);

3) marketing training – peculiarities of the event marketing for the non-commercial organizations; investigation of the competitive environment; corporate style of the university as a component of the image, its stages formation; identification of the professional-managerial orientation of the socio-cultural activity manager; financial resources raising for the project's realization (Svitailo, 2019, p. 5; Kozyr, 2019, p. 6; Yanenko, 2019, p. 6; Boiko, 2019b, p. 6; Nazarov, 2019, p. 6);

4) managerial training – efficiency of the events management and assessment of results; organizational structure of the socio-cultural organizations' sphere management; approaches to the managerial decision-making in the innovative socio-cultural activity management; demand management of the cultural industry production fields; time management (Svitailo, 2019, p. 5; Povalii, 2019, p. 8; Onishchenko, 2019, p. 5; Opanasiuk, 2019, p. 5; Kupenko, 2019, p. 4);

5) organizational training – methodology of staff work organization for the successful event conducting; main trends in the entertainment industry and events organization development; formats of work organization with media and promo actions organization; methodology of people communication organization in the socio-cultural sphere; organization technologies in creative laboratories, workshops, artistic studios, schools, centers of esthetic development and creativity (Svitailo, 2019, pp. 5-6; Povalii, 2019, pp. 4-6);

6) staff training – event-management as an instrument of staff management; competition and cooperation in the teambuilding; corporate culture and staff motivation; basics of teamwork and methodology of teamwork and teambuilding; staff support of project’s implementation (Svitailo, 2019, p. 5; Nazarov, 2019, p. 4; Svitailo & Dementov, 2019, p. 6).

We would like to point out that the content of trainings, methodology, exercises, and cases can vary depending teacher’s professionalization level, group staff, students’ motivation level, academic hours amount, etc. If necessary, teachers can use video and computer facilities for the visualization of individual and group psychological-pedagogical phenomena.

No doubt, training education form is carried out in the process of direct contact between students themselves and between them and a teacher; a teacher acts as a trainer (a person, who combines in himself skills of an expert, an educator, a psychologist, a consultant, a training-manager and a chief), who organizes creative educational activity transforming knowledge and developing student’s creative potential. In the relationships with students, a teacher should use a particular style, showing his personal qualities, and namely (Churkina & Zhadko, 2006, pp. 13-16; Kurtikova et al., 2005, pp. 8-9; Vachkov, 1999): goodwill, openness, purposefulness, quick reaction, flexibility, persistence, acting skills, literacy, charisma, creativity, humor, communicative skills, respect, mindfulness, commitment, observational skills, tolerance, optimism, mental ballast, etc.

Author’s techniques, given by a teacher in the process of training, do not possess photographic reproducibility properties; thus, each of them has a proper idea, a variety of reproduced elements, techniques and details of professional excellence, and namely: speech and voice (tone, power, expressiveness, pronunciation, intonation); mimics, gestures, emotions management, face emotional state understanding; pantomime (posture, ability to stay and sit, to notice students’ behavior); mastery to concentrate on the dialogue’s object, mnemonic technique and autogenous training possessing, stiffness lack; communicative ability (psychological selectivity, ability to pedagogical attention, empathy); pedagogical improvisation (ability to work by the program “in the head”, to use own experience, to manage unplanned circumstances); psychological attention, ability to identify “genius” and support “those, who have fallen behind”; communicative culture, ability to have a conversation, discussion; sense of time (Sergeev et al., 2012).

There have been several various approaches to the education of future sociocultural activity managers in the process of trainings in scientific sources. Moreover, the real practice of teachers’ work proposes more models. In this work, we would like to consider recommendations, which gives candidate of

pedagogical sciences *L. Bondarieva* (2006), and namely: training's preparation – to choose the principal pedagogical idea and connect it to the topic, to define goals and tasks, to select technical means and different forms of work according to goals and tasks, to switch on imagination, to make a detailed plan of the lesson; training's conduction – to speak neither loud, no quiet, but meaningfully with different intonation, not reading a lecture all the time, not converting training into a play only; to use new information technologies, not to be afraid to put difficult questions, to remember training's topic and to stay on it, to manage the audience, to give examples and facts from your experience in your speech, to make a brief analysis of the lesson.

Thus, trainings' implementation in the educational process of socio-cultural activity managers contributes to the creation of a favorable reflexive environment with the possibility of autonomous and conscious search of activity content, information and forecast of further professional development, ways of personal professional realization and competitiveness growth on the labor market. Advantage of the training comparing to traditional forms of future sociocultural activity education is a collective zone of professional development, in which with the help of cooperative mental and practical activity not only reproductive acquisition and prepared professional actions patterns reproduction have been satisfied, but also design and understanding of author's patterns thanks to the participation in discussions and role-plays, group reflection, etc.

4. Conclusions

Results of conducted research allow us to determine the importance of trainings' usage in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers and come to the following conclusions:

1. Retrospective method implementation allowed us to consider key moments in the history of trainings' emergence and development, among which are: Kurt Lewin's creation of the Centre on studying group dynamics in the USA; Kurt Lewin and his students' conducting of trainings in Betel, which were directed to the communicative competence level raise; National training laboratory creation in the United States of America in 1947; training elements implementation in military, religious, and fine arts educational process; K. Stanislavski proposal of numerous exercises for the training of actors; a social and life skills training campaign creation, which was used for the professional education of managers; social-psychological method design in the 70th by M. Forverg.

2. Results of the terminological analysis of the scientific research key concepts of Ukrainian and foreign scientists and dictionary literature allowed us to arrange concept-terminological research apparatus. We also specified the concept “training”, defining it as a model of interactive teaching, directed to the development of necessary personal and business qualities in the short term, motivation guidance, value benchmarks, specialized knowledge, skills, and abilities, which allow raising individual efficiency or competitiveness of an organization. In the context of our research, we consider the concept “training” as an active education form of future managers in the process of which a combination of various socio-cultural activity types is used.

3. We also highlighted the main goal of a training as the creation of conditions for the student’s professional development and self-perfection, in terms of which we can form and master their subject knowledge, as well as declarative and procedural knowledge concerning cultural-leisure programs and cultural-mass events conducting for the different population categories. On the base of this knowledge, we can develop corresponding skills and abilities as components of future socio-cultural activity managers’ professional education.

4. We proved appropriateness of skill-building, personal-oriented, marketing, managerial, organizational and staff trainings in the future socio-cultural activity managers’ education, which give the opportunity to cover different theme blocks of professional information, to diversify educational material, to involve every student to do specific tasks, to build and present own projects properly, etc.

5. We analyzed some algorithms of training’s preparation, and namely: algorithm by T. Fulei, general algorithm, algorithm by Yevgeny Machnyev. Training’s preparation structure in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers has been systematized, which was organized according to the algorithm by T. Fulei and specified under the following indicators: work stages, stages chapters, aim and stages content, application examples.

6. We made the analysis of training’s content, which lies in a group discussion of various professional problems. We determined that training’s main idea is experience transfer and exchange, creation of the artistic and high informative environment, which stimulates the creative and reflexive activity of future specialists. We presented illustrative trainings topics in the contest of future socio-cultural activity managers, which we systematized under trainings types.

7. We determined that in the process of preparation and conduction of training a teacher plays a key role, acting as a trainer (a person, who combines in himself skills of an expert, an educator, a psychologist, a consultant, a training-manager and a chief). We distinguished the teacher’s personal qualities and detected elements of his professional excellence.

Scientific novelty of the obtained results. The scientific novelty of obtained scientific results lies in the specification of the concept “training”, which we consider as a form of interactive education of the future socio-cultural activity managers, and in the process of which we use a complex of various socio-cultural activity types; systematization of the training’s preparation structure in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers under such indicators as work stages, stages sections, aim and contest of the stages, implementation examples; presentation of illustrative trainings topics for the education future socio-cultural activity managers.

The practical significance of the results obtained. The practical significance is in the achievement of the results, which can be used in the educational process of the universities. At the same time, separate points can be used by teachers of the socio-cultural sphere and other specialties according to the specificity of their activity.

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction. The perspective for the future scientific research lies in the profound research of the matters concerning innovative forms and methods of the future socio-cultural activity managers and proper adaptation of modern pedagogical technologies, directed on qualified specialists preparation.

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Information about the Authors:

Olga Boyko, Professor, DSc, Sumy State University, 2 Rimsky-Korsakov Str., Sumy 40007, Ukraine; e-mail: boykoolga0204@ukr.net; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8484-6625> (corresponding author)

Anna Jeremus-Lewandowska, Professor, PhD, Ignacy Jan Paderewski Academy of Music in Poznan, Poznan, Poland; e-mail: annajeremus@poczta.onet.pl; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3278-3818>

Larysa Otroshchenko, Assoc. Professor, PhD, Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine; e-mail: l.otroshchenko@uabs.sumdu.edu.ua; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2333-333X>

Tatiana Povalii, Senior Lecturer, PhD, Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine; e-mail: tatianapovaliy@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5821-9775>